

Universal Agent Archetypes and the Laws of Sociodynamics

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Abstract

In the game-theoretic knowledge domain (Game Theory, Mechanism Design, Social Choice, etc.), Agents have generally been presumed to be instances (Types) of a single Archetype (Class). This pervasive presumption of a single Archetype can directly produce faulty conclusions. This paper advances the claim that every Reflective Agent can be classified by its “strategy” attribute into 1 of 4 distinct Archetypes. These 4 Archetypes (Mutualist, Nihilist, Conformist, Narcissist) are hereby explicitly defined in a structured Taxonomy. Agents of the same Archetype produce similar Outcome spaces, while Agents of different Archetypes produce different Outcome spaces. The Prisoner’s Dilemma (PD) is utilized here to detail the specific effects of Archetype populations in determining Outcomes. The PD analysis reveals that only a homogeneous population of Mutualist Agents consistently produces a Systemic Optimum as the dominant Strategy. This taxonomic Agency effect is invariant across all atomic 2 x 2 Games. A Mutualist Optimum Outcome is therefore systemically optimal, and every Game contains at least 1 Mutualist Optimum.

Keywords: Reflective Agent, Archetype, Agent Class, Agent Taxonomy, Agent Archetype, Game Theory, Mechanism Design, Mutuality, Mutualist

N.B. 1/1/2019: This seminal work of discontinuous innovation was constructed utilizing elements of Systems Science, Social Science, and Mechanism Design Theory integrated into a single interdisciplinary methodology. This unique methodology and the works it produces constitute a new academic discipline, focused primarily on Complex Adaptive Systems of Reflective Agents.

Introduction

In Game Theory, the defining elements are often designated as (N, O, Theta, A, M). where “N” is the number of Agents. “O” is the set of Outcomes. “Theta” is the set of Types. “A” is the available Actions. And “M” is the Mapping of Actions to Outcomes over which Agents have a methodologically individual Utility.

The autonomous Agents in a Game are the causal antecedents of the possible interdependent consequences (Outcomes) they produce. Each one of them has its own private (independent) Type definition (information), which determines the Action an Agent will select. In a Game, the consequences of each Agent’s Actions are dependent upon the Action’s of other Agents. These interdependent consequences are the defining attribute of all social Games. An Agent can be considered “autonomous” if it possesses “Self-directed power, control (decision), and freedom (of Action)” as an intrinsic attribute (methodological individuality).

Prior work in Game Theory has not yet settled upon a standard taxonomy of Agents by Class. Researchers and practitioners generally work under the assumption that there is only a single Class (archetype) for all Agents. This would only be the case if all Agents were exclusively Impulsive (reflexive). In contrast, humans provide an example of Reflective (self-aware | self-deceptive) Agents, which are almost entirely absent from the prior art. Agent definitions can be freely changed to reflect a new set of attributes whenever necessary to modify an analysis/design. The lack of a comprehensive standard can cause problems with comparisons across game settings, and game-theoretic knowledge domains.

Even though every instance of a Reflective Agent has unique Type attributes (utility function, preferences, strategy, etc.), a closer examination reveals that each one can be categorized into 1 of 4 Archetypes (Class) based upon Outcomes produced. The Outcomes of a Game can be significantly altered if such attribute changes result in a change to their Class definition. The set of all Types is designated by Theta with no subscript. This set constitutes a Mob (heterogeneous population). The set of an Archetype (Class) is simply designated with a subscript. All instances of an Archetype constitute a homogeneous population.

An Agent’s attributes are in direct correlation with the Outcomes produced by that Agent’s individual attribute set. It’s therefore important in all Game analysis/design to explicitly relate Agent Archetype to the Outcomes that Class will produce. To construct such a generally applicable tool requires development of a standardized taxonomy that encodes all possible Agent attributes based upon Outcomes. The proposed Agent Taxonomy provides such a standardized tool.

The only prior work in Game Theory to focus specifically on the categorization of Agents by their attributes and its impact on Outcomes was presented by Rapoport [1]. The primary difference is that Rapoport’s proposed “Archetypes” were still incomplete. They don’t appear to be intended for general application, and the work doesn’t seem to have been pursued any further. The Agent Taxonomy proposed here is intended to provide a general standard for all social Games.

Because it’s an essential element of Agency, the following taxonomy model provides a comprehensive definition of Impulse and Reflection as the motivational drivers for all autonomous Agent Actions. Reflective Agents are capable of bilateral rationality, in contrast to an Impulsive Agent, which is only capable of unilateral rationality. Since fictitious agents (States, corporations, etc.) are analogs (legal fictions) of actual “persons”, their Agency is also defined by this model.

Motivation Taxonomy

Results

Given any Game with interdependent Outcomes and individual utility functions for each Agent, Table 1 provides a comprehensive taxonomy of autonomous Agents. In Table 1, “Rationality” refers specifically to decision-theoretic rationality.

Reflective Agent Taxonomy						
Class	Preference		Rationality	Social Ethic	Strict Entry	Motive
	utility_{self}	utility_{other}				
Mutualist	Optimum	Optimum	Bilateral	Stewardship	Yes	Reflection
Narcissist	Optimum	Indifferent (or not optimum)	Unilateral (self)	Sovereignty	No	Impulse
Conformist	Indifferent (or not optimum)	Optimum	Unilateral (other)	Servitude	No	Impulse
Nihilist	Indifferent (or not optimum)	Indifferent (or not optimum)	Irrational	Relativism	No	Alienation

Table 1: Reflective Agent Taxonomy by Utility

The Narcissist Class has been well established in the Game Theory domain, while the other Classes are much less commonly evaluated. This class provides a useful analog of a purely Impulsive Agent (reflexive), which is devoid of Reflection, like most animals. Each Class has unique characteristics that produce unique Outcomes by all instances of that Class.

The Mutualist Class provides the opportunity for innovations in Game Theory due to the unique Outcomes produced by the holistic bilateral preference. The utility function of a Mutualist is executed by first establishing the ordinals of the unilateral (Narcissist) preference tuple for each individual Agent. These are then utilized to determine the mutual utility (mutual preference) of each potential

Outcome (cell) as determined by the following function in Table 2.

Mutualist Utility Function (narrative form):
Optimize total aggregate utility while simultaneously optimizing equity (parity, equality, etc.) of utility.
Mutualist Utility Function (2 x 2 ordinal form):
$u = ((x_i + y_i) + x_i - y_i) / 2$: where x_i = Agent R utility ordinal (Narcissistic) and y_i = Agent C utility ordinal (Narcissistic).

Table 2: Mutualist Utility Function Definition

A review of all the possible Agent populations (by Class) provides a complete survey of the Outcome space produced, based upon the Prisoner's Dilemma (PD). The results can be seen in Table 3. The term "Iteration Stable" means Agent strategy will persist if the Game is repeated. The "?" symbol indicates an unpredictable (random, irrational, inconsistent, etc.) parameter.

Outcomes Space (PD)				
Game Population (heterogeneous)	Outcome Attributes			
	Preference Satisfied	Optimum Outcome	Iteration Stable	Common Class
	(R C)	(Systemic)	(Game)	
1. R is Mutualist, C is Narcissist				
R prefers Q1, gets Q3 C prefers Q3, gets Q3	N Y	N	N	N
2. R is Mutualist, C is Conformist				
R prefers Q1, gets Q1 C prefers Q2, gets Q1	Y N	Y	N	N
3. R is Mutualist, C is Nihilist				
R prefers Q1, gets ? C prefers ?, gets ?	? ?	?	N	N
4. R is Narcissist, C is Conformist				
R prefers Q2, gets Q2 C prefers Q2, gets Q2	Y Y	N	Y	N
5. R is Narcissist, C is Nihilist				
R prefers Q2, gets ? C prefers ?, gets ?	? ?	?	N	N
6. R is Conformist, C is Nihilist				
R prefers Q3, gets ? C prefers ?, gets ?	? ?	?	N	N
Game Population (homogeneous)				
7. R is Mutualist, C is Mutualist				
R prefers Q1, gets Q1 C prefers Q1, gets Q1	Y Y	Y	Y	Y
8. R is Narcissist, C is Narcissist				
R prefers Q2, gets Q4 C prefers Q3, gets Q4	N N	N	N	Y
9. R is Conformist, C is Conformist				
R prefers Q3, gets Q1 C prefers Q2, gets Q1	N N	Y	N	Y
10. R is Nihilist, C is Nihilist				
R prefers ?, gets ? C prefers ?, gets ?	? ?	?	N	Y

Table 3: Outcomes Space for the Prisoner's Dilemma by Agent Class (Archetype)

It can be seen in the table that Mutualist Agents are uniquely obligated to avoid (Not Enter, Exit, Opt Out, etc.) participation in any Game with non-Mutualist Agents. This is necessary in order to prevent a paradox (antithesis/contradiction) for the Mutualist Class definition. If forced (or accidentally engaged) into a Game with non-Mutualists, a Mutualist preferred Action is to Exit (opt out) as soon as possible.

Discussion

It can be seen in the Outcomes Space for PD (Table 3) that the only Game design that will produce consistent optimum Outcomes is one in which there is a homogeneous population of Mutualist Agents.

A population of Mutualist Class Agents produces unique optimization Outcomes that none of the other Classes can produce. All Mutualist Optimums are Pareto Optimums, but all Pareto Optimums are not necessarily Mutualist Optimums. A homogenous population of Mutualist Agents intrinsically converge

to a Mutual (Systemic) Optimum as the dominant Strategy in any Game. Table 4 provides a summary of the potential optimizations.

Mutualist Outcomes (optimality)	
Form	Description
Mutual Optimum	Outcome that has a better (or equal) preference ordinal than all other Outcome ordinals.
Strict Mutual Optimum	Outcome that has a better (but not equal) preference ordinal than all other Outcome ordinals.
Ideal Mutual Optimum	Outcome that has a preference ordinal of “1”.

Table 4: Optimality for Homogeneous Mutualist Population

It’s important to note that Mutualist utility always produces equal (twin) ordinals for both of the Agents in each Outcome pair, such that $x_i = y_i$ in every cell (quadrant). In this case there is a Strict Mutual Optimum dyad in the Outcome (2,2). This is one example where a Mutualist Agent in a homogenous PD Game consistently produces a Strict Mutual Optimum (a Pareto Optimum) as a strict dominant Strategy. Mutualists require knowledge of Other's Ordinal Preference Map in order to choose an Action (Strategy) accurate to their Class attributes.

A Mutual Optimum is one where everyone can’t be made better off without making one of the participants worse off. In Games where there is not a Strict Mutual Optimum, some form of cooperation is required to coordinate the Action to be selected from among the equivalent Mutual Optimums. If these Games are repeated, a Mutualist strategy requires sequential iteration over the equivalent options (round robin). Such a Game Setting requires “memory” and “message” mechanisms.

If this Archetype taxonomy proves to be sufficiently comprehensive, accurate, and internally consistent, then it provides an empirical nucleus for Social Science. This nucleus can provide a set of functions similar to those that Thermodynamics provides for Natural Science. Based upon a fully integrated encoding of the UAA principles, a model for the Laws of Sociodynamics can therefore be constructed as follows.

First Law: All consequences are interdependent, to the extent of their circumstantial proximity [Sharing principle].

Second Law: Every Reflective Agent is an instance of 1 of 4 Archetypes; Conformist, Mutualist, Narcissist, Nihilist [Agency principle].

Third Law: An Ideal Mutual Outcome is impossible in a Zero Sum Game [Conflict principle].

Fourth Law: Justice (Scientific) - is the realization of systemic optimization [Optimization principle].

Fifth Law: Truth - is the most Complete, Accurate, Relevant, Simple (CARS) interpretation of Reality [Convergence principle].

Sixth Law: Power that serves justice is systemically constructive, Power that does not is systemically destructive [Action principle].

Seventh Law: Life is a Game of Games (System of Systems), each one defined by 6 elements: Arena, Rules, Roles, Resources, Referees, and Entry/Exit. [Organizing principle].

Zerorth Law: All beliefs are imaginary, but some are useful [Absurdity principle].

Commentary

The First Law: encodes the observation that all consequences (outcomes, events, effects, results, etc.) are dependent upon all other consequences, even if the reciprocal interactivity is infinitesimally small. Past circumstances, remote circumstances, unknown circumstances, and other such state variables are all dependent upon each other (causal chaining). The circumstances of proximity (Mass-Energy, Information, Space-Time) generally determines the extent (quantity/quality) of interdependence.

The Second Law: encodes the observation that every reflective agent is an instance of 1 of the 4 universal Archetypes (Class) of agency, based upon their primary strategy (preferences, motivations, etc.). Traditionally, the philosophy of Social Science has almost exclusively presumed Narcissist instances of agents in all models. A complete data matrix defining the full range of possible agent Archetypes is essential as the foundational basis for this Law. [Such a taxonomy of Agency can be found in “Universal Agent Archetypes”, 2010, Table 1: Agent Taxonomy; M. Urban]

The Third Law: encodes the observation that a Zero Sum Game can never result in an outcome where all participating Agents achieve their highest individual preference. This is true because of the defining characteristic of such Games (Systems). Once a Zero Sum Game event occurs (intentionally or unintentionally), there is no longer an ideal, mutual, optimum consequence (outcome) available to the participants. The highest level of conflict resolution that can be achieved under such circumstances is a mutual compromise (the second best preference for all). [Games/Systems (social) are fully modeled in Mutuality Book II - Encyclopedia, 2010 Edition; M. Urban]

The Fourth Law: encodes the observation that the means for achieving Justice (scientific/empirical), is through systemic optimization. Legitimate Laws (rules, policies, etc.) arise from conscientious adherence to Justice. A homogeneous association of Mutualist Agents inherently produces Justice. Other Archetype associations, and heterogeneous associations, eventually drive their respective systems into sub-optimal (unjust, unfair) states. Some individual Agents may benefit in such sub-optimal systems, but most participants will realize less beneficial outcomes than they would have been able to realize in an optimized system (except by random coincidence).

The Fifth Law: encodes the observation that Reality and its relevant interpretations are distinct, and yet fully interdependent. Identification of Truth requires the input of many qualified Points of View, all of them collaborating to reach a point of convergence regarding the interpretation. The CARS (Complete, Accurate, Relevant, Simple) paradigm fully encodes the underlying principles of the well known justice oath: “the Truth, the whole Truth, and nothing but the Truth”. [A complete Truth methodology can be found in Mutuality Book I - Methodology, 2010 Edition; M. Urban].

The Sixth Law: encodes the observation that unless Power (personal, social) is utilized to serve Justice, there is a high probability that its use will produce systemic harm (net). Any use of Power that doesn't serve Justice is systemically sub-optimal, by definition. Therefore, a unified definition of Justice

(Fairness) is an essential precondition for establishing universal parameters for constructive (legitimate, beneficial, good, etc.) use of Power and destructive (illegitimate, harmful, evil, etc.) use. [A universal standard for Power can be found in Mutuality Book II - Encyclopedia, 2010 Edition; M. Urban].

The Seventh Law: encodes the observation that social Games (Systems) spontaneously emerge from the circumstantial proximity of autonomous Agents, in a standard structure. The elements of this structure may be actual or virtual in nature. They are defined as Arena (boundary, context), Rules (laws, regulations), Roles (functions, relationships), Resources (natural, sociofacts), Referees (arbitration, judgment), Entry/Exit (inclusion, exclusion). [A full treatment of Games (Systems) and their elements can be found in Mutuality Book II - Encyclopedia, 2010 Edition; M. Urban].

The Zeroth Law: encodes the observation that imagination (internalized, symbolic analogy) is the foundational result of all interpretations (models, cognitive maps, points of view, frameworks, paradigms, etc.) of Reality . We construct our internal interpretations of Reality through self-constructed analogies, along with their various sub-components (symbols, language, emotions, etc.). It's important to remember at all times that a map is not the territory, and that it only needs to provide a useful representation to achieve its optimal functionality. Models of Reality (Worldview, POV, Weltanschauung) are not actual Reality itself, only the imaginings of it. This meta-Law therefore informs all of the other Laws, which collectively encode the criteria for what constitutes being “useful”.

Methodology

The following are the specifics for the results based upon the well known PD. All 2 x 2 Game transformations have been tested, but are not included here. Only the PD example is reconstructed here to analyze the effects of a homogeneous population of Mutualist Agents on the traditional PD Outcome.

In Game analysis, the ordinals of Narcissist utility for each Narcissist Agent are determined from their individual cardinal payoff preferences, as detailed for the PD in the following table.

Ordinal Map for Prisoner's Dilemma (unilateral _{self})	
Payoff (utility)	Ordinal (preference rank)
Jail time = 1 yr	1 (best)
Jail time = 2 yr	2
Jail time = 3 yr	3
Jail time = 4 yr	4 (worst)

Table 5: Mapping of Cardinal Utility to Ordinal Utility for PD

Utilizing these ordinal utilities, a traditional PD Game (homogeneous Narcissist population) produces the following Outcomes (in ordinal form).

Game Matrix (ordinal form)			
(Prisoner's Dilemma, 2 Narcissists)			
		Agent C	
		silent	confess
Agent R	silent	(2,2)	(1,4)
	confess	(4,1)	(3,3)

Table 6: Traditional PD Outcomes In The Ordinal Form

The 4 Possible Outcomes by cell (Q_i)
Q ₁ = Pareto Optimum (best case) – (2,2)
Q ₂ = Suboptimal and disparity (stratification) – (1,4)
Q ₃ = Suboptimal and disparity (stratification) – (4,1)
Q ₄ = Nash Equilibrium (race to the bottom) (3,3)

Table 7: Outcomes Analysis for PD

In the standard PD, both Agents will select Action “confess”. It can be seen in this standard version of the PD Game that there are 2 Narcissistic prisoners equilibrated in a dominant strategy (Action) dilemma in which they both could be better off Acting otherwise. This produces the well known dilemma of such unilateral utility (preferences). The Optimum Outcome for both Agents is not dominant unless some other Game parameters or a utility function manipulation is introduced. The Agents victimize themselves in a race to the bottom (sub-optimum equilibrium) with each other.

If the 2 Narcissist Agents are replaced by 2 Mutualist Agents and the Game is played, the optimum (mutual) Outcome is intrinsically dominant and the dilemma is avoided. The following represents the Outcomes from the PD Game that result for a homogeneous Mutualist population.

Game Matrix (ordinal form)			
(Prisoner's Dilemma, 2 Mutualists)			
		Agent C	
		silent	confess
Agent R	silent	(2,2)	(4,4)
	confess	(4,4)	(3,3)

Table 8: PD Outcomes, Homogeneous Mutualist Population

Conclusions

A standard taxonomy for all Agents can be a useful tool in Game Theory and its related disciplines (Mechanism Design, Social Choice, Consumer Theory, etc.). No other standard taxonomy of Agents appears to be widely recognized at this time. Such a tool can unify work across knowledge domains.

Since the actual consequences (real Outcomes) of a Game are interdependent. And because Agent attributes determine Outcomes. It can be critical for complete Game analysis/design to consider all standard Agent Classes.

These 4 simple Class definitions encode the most critical elements for determining Outcomes that relevant Agents will produce. Within each Class, there can be a wide spectrum of specific attributes (utility functions, preferences, rationality, etc.) assigned to each Agent Type. There are no relevant Agent attribute sets based upon Utility (strategy) that fall outside of this Agent Taxonomy.

Bibliography

1. Rapoport, Anatol. "Exploiter, Leader, Hero, and Martyr: The Four Archetypes of the 2x2 Game." Systems Research and Behavioral Science, Vol. 12:2 (1967:Mar), pp 81.